

Article

“Low-Hanging Fruit” Practices for Improving Water Productivity of Rainfed Potatoes Using Integration of Cultivar Selection, Mulch Application, and Different Agroecological Zones in Sub-Tropical, Semi-Arid Regions

Nosipho Precious Minenhle Phungula ^{1,*}, Sandile Thamsanqa Hadebe ² , Elmar Schulte-Geldermann ³, Lucky Sithole ⁴ and Nomali Ziphorah Ngobese ⁵

¹ Department of Science, Botany and Plant Biotechnology, University of Johannesburg, P.O. Box 524, Auckland Park 2006, South Africa

² Department of Plant Production, Soil Science and Agricultural Engineering, University of Limpopo, Private Bag Box X1106, Sovenga 0727, South Africa; sandile.hadebe@ul.ac.za

³ University of Applied Science Bingen (TH Bingen), Berlinstrasse 109, 55411 Bingen am Rhein, Germany; e.schulte-geldermann@th-bingen.de

⁴ Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, Pietermaritzburg 3245, South Africa; lucky.sithole@kzndard.gov.za

⁵ Unit for Environmental Sciences and Management, Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences, North-West University, Private Bag X6001, Potchefstroom 2520, South Africa; nomali.ngobese@nwu.ac.za

* Correspondence: minenhlephungula6@gmail.com

Abstract: Unevenly distributed rainfall leads to reduced potato water productivity (WP) under rainfed production conditions. Understanding the practices that can increase WP is vital. Our objectives were to understand (i) the seasonal variables that influence WP under rainfed conditions and (ii) the effect of the integration of cultivar × locality × mulch on potato WP. The study was undertaken in smallholder settings in two agroecological zones: Appelsbosch (Mbalenhle locality) and Swayimane (Stezi and Mbhava locality). A split plot, in a randomized complete block design experiment, included mulching (mulch and no mulch), four selected cultivars, and three localities. Soil water content (SWC), yield, and climatic data were collected, and actual crop evapotranspiration (ET_a) and WP were calculated. Rainfall, ET_a, and crop growth and development had a significant influence on the seasonal WP. Cultivar × mulch × locality had an insignificant effect on the WP, however, locality × cultivar significantly altered the WP. The localities that had lower vapor pressure deficit (VPD), high relative humidity, and sandy soil had a higher potato WP for all cultivars, with the highest (18.38 kg m⁻³) being that from Electra. The findings suggest that using localities that have less atmospheric dryness and a cultivar (Electra) that shows stability of yield across the seasons can be an easy-to-apply practice for increasing potato WP in a resource-limited environment.

Keywords: evapotranspiration; soil water content; atmospheric dryness; rainfall variability; yield

Citation: Phungula, N.P.M.; Hadebe, S.T.; Schulte-Geldermann, E.; Sithole, L.; Ngobese, N.Z. “Low-Hanging Fruit” Practices for Improving Water Productivity of Rainfed Potatoes Using Integration of Cultivar Selection, Mulch Application, and Different Agroecological Zones in Sub-Tropical, Semi-Arid Regions. *Water* **2024**, *16*, 3422. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16233422>

Academic Editor: Arturo Alvino

Received: 12 September 2024

Revised: 23 November 2024

Accepted: 26 November 2024

Published: 28 November 2024

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

Water productivity (WP) is the ratio of yield or biomass produced per unit of actual water used [1]. Potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) WP in the sub-Saharan African (SSA) region has been reported, particularly in Ethiopia, as ranging from 3.56 to 8.70 kg m⁻³ [2]; in contrast, in the Asia region (Pakistan), it ranged from 14.60 to 17.28 kg m⁻³ [3]. The low potato yield of 6 to 10 t ha⁻¹ in the SSA [4] region results in low WP, which is exacerbated by rainfall variability accompanied by flash floods and intermittent dry spells. This results in water losses and crop water stress during the growing season, causing inefficient water use and decreases in yield [5]. Consequently, SSA farming under rainfed conditions is at risk due to climatic variability given the heavy dependence on rainfall. Moreover, rainfall

does not match crop water demands at each growth stage, often creating a mismatch between the required potato water distribution and the level of rainfall occurring [5]. Potatoes require the least amounts of water from planting to crop establishment, with a crop coefficient (K_c) of 0.4–0.5, and this increases as the crop moves towards crop maturity and harvest ($K_c = 0.7$ – 0.75) [6]. Water requirements gradually increase ($K_c = 0.7$ – 0.8) during the crop development phase due to vegetative growth and the initiation of tuber development. Water requirements peak at the mid-season phase ($K_c = 1.05$ – 1.2), when peak photosynthesis and tuber bulking occurs [6]. Resource-constrained SSA potato producers usually lack irrigation inputs, making potato production under such settings highly reliant on rainfall. This means they are exposed to rainfall-related production risks, especially when rainfall is a limiting factor [7].

Improving potato WP under rainfed growing conditions is linked to management practices related to changes in crop, soil, and water. These practices include retaining and storing water during flash flood events to ensure sufficient water during dry spells. They also include covering the soil with mulch to conserve soil moisture, increase infiltration during heavy rain, reduce soil evaporation, and restrain runoff [8]. This practice simultaneously improves crop growth and water productivity; furthermore, the existing literature reported an increase in WP through utilizing mulch [9–13] from different settings. However, there is very low use of mulch by SSA smallholder farmers, particularly in South Africa. Biswal et al. [13] reported that straw mulching significantly increased water productivity (30–39%). Over and above that, another tool to improve WP is to select an environment (locality) that offers moderate temperatures, adequate rainfall, and fewer extreme events that are accompanied by high atmospheric dryness, a factor that amplifies dry spell severity and soil moisture deficit during potato production, thereby negatively affecting plant water fluxes and crop yields [14].

Approximately 96% of smallholder farmers use low-quality seeds: either potatoes retained from the previous harvest (farmer-saved seed), sourced from neighbors, or purchased from local markets [15,16]. Poor-quality seeds from the informal sector are generally less efficient in converting water into biomass and, ultimately, into yield. This results in higher water usage per unit of yield produced, reducing overall water productivity. Therefore, to increase the yield of potatoes for each unit of water transpired, the adoption of certified seed from improved cultivars is key to improving WP. Breeders have developed a range of cultivars that match growth cycles with the expected water supply or with the absence of crop hazards, and which are tolerant to water stresses such as dry spells [17]. For instance, selecting short- to medium-duration cultivars increases WP by allowing the plants to escaping the late-season water stresses that adversely affect potato growth and development. Meanwhile, late-maturing cultivars can utilize the late-season rainfall. Farmers have the option to select cultivars that are customized to fit local climatic conditions, and to select localities that have certain soil types or hydrological properties that have been noted to help a farmer improve WP.

The application of mulch and cultivar selection to improve potato WP in different agroecological zones has been reported on by a handful of studies [9,10,18–20]. Despite the solution being put forward, the practices mentioned tend to give small investment returns when individually applied. Mulch is used as a water-saving strategy and it conserves soil moisture, regulates soil temperature, and suppresses weeds. Meanwhile, improved cultivars have the ability to use resources efficiently and increase potato yield. Lastly, various localities have diverse climatic conditions and soils, allowing for adaptation and good yield performance. These insights suggest that, with integrated practices, potato WP can be improved, and that practices assist one another to achieve better performance. This approach corresponds to the concept of producing “more crops per drop” by increasing output when little water is used, reducing loss of water through evaporation and other

unproductive processes, and, lastly, improving the efficient use of rainfall. This integration of factors has not been studied, especially in the smallholder setting, which has low yield, translating to low WP. Therefore, the specific objectives were to determine (i) the seasonal variable's influence on seasonal potato WP under dryland conditions and (ii) the impact of the integration of cultivar selection, the application of mulch at different levels, and the locality on potato WP. Furthermore, this study contributes to knowledge regarding the selection of cultivars that can improve potato WP and the practices that can be used to achieve high yields and WP for potatoes in smallholder settings. In South Africa, there is limited knowledge of the practices that are used by smallholder farmers and statistics regarding potato yield are very difficult to obtain for this setting, so this study will cover that research gap.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Potato Cultivars' Selection

The potato cultivars (Table 1) Mondial, Sababa, Panamera, and Electra were sourced from Wesgrow (Pty) Ltd, Christiana, South Africa. Cultivars that were selected varied in terms of season length and drought tolerance. The maturation period (in days) was observed in the field for the current study.

Table 1. Cultivars of the study's characteristics.

Cultivar	Drought Tolerance	Length of the Growing Season	Maturation Period (Days)
Electra ¹	Good	Medium late	119–126
Mondial ¹	Good	Medium late	119–126
Panamera ¹	Susceptible	Late	132–142
Sababa ²	Good	Medium	112–120

Note: Source: ¹ [20]; ² [21].

2.2. Field Description and Climate Data

The field trials were conducted in two different agroecological zones in Swayimane (Stezi and Mbhava) and Appelsbosch (Mbalenhle) in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa (Figure 1). Swayimane and Appelsbosch represented macro-climatically different agroecological regions. Appelsbosch has a cooler, highly humid, drier climate, with lower-clay-content soils that are sandy loam in texture (Tables 2 and 3). On the other hand, Swayimane has a warmer, moderately humid, wetter climate with high-clay-content soils that are sandy clay in texture (Tables 2 and 3). Swayimane was further divided into two different micro-climatic localities (Stezi and Mbhava) even though both regions are under the same bioresource group (BRG) (Table 2). Stezi is on a high-lying (hilltop), warmer, north-facing (sun-facing) slope (Table 2). Ironically, Stezi means high heights, which matches the description of a high-lying area in this instance. Stezi was expected to have high atmospheric dryness due to its warmer and drier atmosphere compared to Mbhava. Mbhava is in a low-lying (valley), on a cooler, south-facing slope (Table 2). Before initiating planting, automatic weather stations (AWS) (Davis 6152 Wireless Vantage Pro 2) were installed on the experimental sites, and data such as temperature, rainfall, reference evapotranspiration (ET_o), and relative humidity were collected. The ET_o was calculated daily according to FAO Penman–Monteith's method [6]. Furthermore, characterization of soil testing was performed to determine soil form, soil depth, and soil hydraulic properties [22] for each experiment before planting. Afterward, the SPAW model [23] was used to obtain volumetric soil water content at field capacity (FC), permanent wilting point (PWP), and saturation (SAT). The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Bioresource group classification and climate information for the Appelsbosch and Swayimane planting sites.

Macro-Climature (Agroecologies)	Appelsbosch		Swayimane
Micro-climate (locality)	Mbalenhle	Stezi	Mbhava
Coordinates	29°22'33.88" S 30°52'4.84" E	29°31'51.10" S 30°35'24.42" E	29°33'54.98" S 30°39'44.64" E
Elevation (m.a.s.l)	1003	874	750
Average air temperatures (°C) ^{1,2}	17.1	18.7	18.7
Humidity levels ^{1,2}	High	Moderate	Moderate
Annual mean and range of rainfall (mm) ^{1,2}	650 (500–800) ¹	800 (600–1100) ²	800 (600–1100) ²
Aspect	North-facing slope	North-facing slope	South-facing slope
Bioresource group (BRU) ^{3,4}	Warm moist grass veld	Sub-tropical coastal	Sub-tropical coastal

Note: ¹ [24], ² [25], ³ [26], ⁴ [27]

Table 3. Localities' soil properties descriptions.

Locality	Soil Depth (m)	Soil Form	Textural Class	Clay Content	¹ PWP %	² FC	³ SAT
Mbalenhle	>1	Inanda (Umbrisols)	Sandy loam	20.7	22.1	33.7	43.7
Mbhava	>1	Hutton (Ferralsols)	Clay	50.4	29.5	39.9	42.0
Stezi	>1	Inanda (Umbrisols)	Sandy clay loam	26.6	23.1	39.1	46.7

Note: ¹ Permanent wilting point, ² field capacity, and ³ saturation.

Figure 1. The study area shows three localities (Stezi, Mbhava, and Mbalenhle).

2.3. Experimental Design and Field Management

Soil samples were collected at each site for soil fertility analysis. Analysis was performed at Cedara Soil Analytical Services [28] and fertilizer (KCl and 2:3:4 (30)) was applied using the soil fertility analysis. The field trial was in the 2022/23 and 2023/24 planting seasons (August to January) in the above-mentioned localities (micro-climates). A split-plot layout was used in a randomized complete block design. Mulch level (no mulch and mulch), locality (Mbhava, Stezi and Mbalenhle), and cultivars (Panamera, Electra, Sababa, and Mondial) were tested. The pre-sprouted seeds were manually planted in four rows on a plot with a spacing of 0.3 m × 0.9 m. Upon reaching crop establishment stage, 1.9 kg m⁻² mulch was applied evenly, and dry hay grass (mixture of grasses such as brome, Bermuda, and rye) was used as mulch; this type of grass is abundantly available in rural homesteads. Dithane M45 (3 kg ha⁻¹), Ridomil (2.5 L ha⁻¹), and Bravo (1 L ha⁻¹) fungicides were used weekly to control blight diseases upon disease incidence. The insects were controlled as well using Cypermethrin and Decis at a rate of 0.150 L ha⁻¹ [29]. Weeds were manually removed during the growing season, and Glyphosate (5 L ha⁻¹) was only used before plowing the soil [30].

2.4. Collection of Field-Measured Variables

2.4.1. Growth and Phenological Parameters

An image of the canopy cover was collected using the Canopeo v2.0 application: the captured high-resolution image and the application evaluated pixels of the image based on the red-to-green (R/G) and blue-to-green (B/G) color ratios [30]. The resulting output image is in black and white; the green area is represented by white and black represents the non-green area. Thereby, maximum canopy cover was the highest percentage of canopy cover; meanwhile, duration of maximum canopy cover was the number of days between maximum canopy decline and days when maximum canopy cover was reached. At harvest, yield was measured on the experimental plot's two center rows.

2.4.2. Actual Crop Evapotranspiration (ET_a)

Soil water content (SWC) was measured using a Diviner 2000 (Sentek Environmental Technologies, Stepney, Australia) through PVC access tubes that were installed at the center of the plots; the first reading was taken on the day of planting, followed by weekly measurements. Last reading was at harvest. The readings were performed on different depth intervals of 10, 20, 30, 30, 40, 60, 70, 80, 90, and 100 cm as the percentage of soil water content. Furthermore, changes in soil water content (Δ SWC) are the difference between soil water content at planting and harvest. Moreover, actual crop evapotranspiration/water use (ET_a) was calculated using the soil water balance Equation (1).

$$ET_a = P - D \pm \Delta SWC \quad (1)$$

where ET_a is actual crop evapotranspiration, P is rainfall, and D is drainage. In the current study, drainage was minimal and was considered zero when soil profile moisture storage was less than field capacity. When soil water content exceeded the field capacity after rainfall, drainage was calculated as the difference between the field capacity storage and soil water content plus rainfall [31], and SWC is the change in soil water content. The study was conducted under rainfed conditions; hence, irrigation was ignored, and runoff and capillary rise were negligible. The cultivars reached physiological maturity on different days, hence, rainfall used to calculate ET_a was based on days to reach maturity. Thereby, water productivity (WP) was calculated using the following Equation (4):

$$WP = \text{Yield}/ET_a \quad (2)$$

2.4.3. Vapor Pressure Deficit

The vapor pressure deficit was calculated with the following Equations (3)–(6) [32]:

$$e^{\circ}(T) = 0.6108 \exp \left[\frac{17.27T}{T + 273.3} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$e_s = \frac{e^{\circ}(T_{\max}) + e^{\circ}(T_{\min})}{2} \quad (4)$$

$$e_a = \frac{e^{\circ}(T_{\min}) \frac{RH_{\max}}{100} + e^{\circ}(T_{\max}) \frac{RH_{\min}}{100}}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$VPD = e_s - e_a \quad (6)$$

where $e^{\circ}(T)$ is the saturation vapor pressure at air temperature T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), T_{\max} is the daily maximum temperature, T_{\min} is the minimum temperature, RH_{\max} is the maximum relative humidity, RH_{\min} is the minimum relative humidity, e_s is saturated vapor pressure, e_a is actual vapor pressure, and VPD is vapor pressure deficit.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

GenStat software (GenStat[®], 23rd edition [64 Bit] VSNi International Ltd, Hemel Hempstead, UK) was used to analyze data. Tukey was used for the mean separation test at $p < 0.05$. The association of seasonal variables was correlated using GenStat.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Potato Cultivars' Response to Weather Data

The optimum temperatures for potato growth are 7–20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [33]; the obtained minimum temperature ranged from 4.6 to 6.9 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ across localities with no cold stresses. Temperatures were low at the beginning of the season but became warmer as the season progressed, with no observation of heat stress (Figure 2). Both seasons received a high amount of seasonal rainfall, ranging from 540 to 774 mm, however, both seasons' received rainfall was unevenly distributed between dry spells and did not match crop coefficient (Kc) water requirements. A huge amount of rainfall was received in the late-season stage (Figure 2) when it was not needed in abundance. Hence, the rainfed setting is at risk and vulnerable to this climatic variability. The localities showed similar rainfall patterns, however, Mbalenhle received more rainfall (235 mm) for the 2023/24 season in the development stage compared to other localities, and this is the stage where tubers start to form, and when adequate moisture is important. In both growing seasons, reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) (56 to 99 mm) was higher than rainfall at the initial stage, except for Stezi in 2022/23. Here, the high atmospheric demand simply translated into water deficit in the soil, exposing the potato plants to intermittent drought [14]. The low seasonal average relative humidity (61.4% and 66.4%) and high vapor pressure deficit (1.08 kPa and 1.14 kPa) observed in Mbhava for both seasons (Table 4) led to higher atmospheric dryness, hence, the daily average reference evapotranspiration (ET_o) was 4 mm day⁻¹ (Figure 2). This locality, therefore, had a drier atmosphere for potato growth, which might have affected crop transpiration. Mbhava had higher ET_o than other localities, indicating higher atmospheric water demand, which reduced water available. This negatively accelerated soil evaporation and transpiration, leading to higher crop actual evapotranspiration. Meanwhile, Stezi and Mbalenhle were humid with an average daily VPD of 0.82 to 0.83 kPa and 0.74 to 0.78 kPa (Table 4). The high relative humidity for Stezi and Mbalenhle led to less atmospheric dryness, hence, the daily average ET_o was 3 mm day⁻¹ for both the 2022/23 and 2023/24 seasons for Stezi and Mbalenhle. The observed climatic data further emphasize that sufficient seasonal rainfall is not important compared to the even distribution of rainfall proportionate with Kc. Hence, farmers can shift planting dates to make use of the huge amounts of rainfall received in the late season.

Figure 2. Weather data [rainfall, relative humidity (RH), reference evapotranspiration (ETo), and air temperature] distribution according to growth stages [initial stage (IS), development stage (DS), mid-season stage (MS), and late-season stage (LS)] of the two growing seasons (2022/23 and 2023/24), for Mbalenhle, Mbhava, and Stezi.

Table 4. Daily average vapor pressure deficit across two growing seasons (kPa day⁻¹).

Locality	2022/23 Season	2023/24 Season
Mbalenhle	0.78	0.74
Mbhava	1.08	1.14
Stezi	0.82	0.83

3.2. Seasonal Variation in Crop Water Productivity

There were highly significant ($p < 0.001$) variations in water productivity (WP) between the seasons (Table 5), and WP was higher in the 2023/24 season (10.63 kg m⁻³) compared to the 2022/23 season (9.09 kg m⁻³) (Figure 3A). The variations in seasonal water productivity were driven primarily by highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) differences in crop actual evapotranspiration (ETa) between seasons since yields were statistically similar across seasons ($p = 0.556$) (Table 5). Crop actual evapotranspiration was significantly higher in the 2022/23 season (363 mm) and lower during the 2023/24 season (260 mm) (Figure 3C), while the yields were 39.36 t ha⁻¹ and 39.97 t ha⁻¹ (Figure 3B). Water productivity was significantly and negatively correlated ($r = -0.64$) with ETa (Table 6), therefore, increased ETa resulted in a decrease in potato WP. Hence, the results indicate that high ETa does not necessarily improve potato WP but can result in increased water use, where more water is lost to the atmosphere and through drainage rather than being used for plant growth [34]. The differences in ETa have been caused by rainfall; there were highly significant ($p < 0.001$) variations where rainfall received was higher in the 2022/23 season (573 mm) compared to the 2023/24 season (533 mm) (Figure 3D). This can be further explained by the strong correlation ($r = 0.89$) between rainfall and ETa. Both seasons received high rainfall, however, it was erratic, with uneven distribution. For instance, the mid-season of the 2022/23 season had higher rainfall (182 mm) than the 2023/24 season, which had 136 mm (Figure 4). This stage is critical because potatoes are bulking and Kc is high, hence, water demand is high. Therefore, the rainfall received did not match the water demand, and this further elaborates the fact that, at this stage, the 2023/24 season used water efficiently according to crop needs and the plots were able to utilize the lower rainfall received with no water stress being observed. Furthermore, a high amount of available water was not all used efficiently by the crop; some of it was lost through unproductive processes such as soil evaporation and drainage, particularly in the presence of erratic rainfall. Season 2 (2023/24) was noted to have a high maximum canopy cover (Figure 3E) and a longer duration of maximum canopy cover (Figure 3F), hence, foliage was able to cover the soil and reduce unproductive loss of water, such as soil evaporation, and that might have contributed to low ETa. Understanding the influence of these variables on potato WP is crucial for enabling farmers to improve management practices. The results revealed that ETa and rainfall significantly influenced WP, hence, improving ETa under rainfed conditions by adopting practices that conserve and regulate soil moisture and selecting potato cultivars that can use water efficiently might lead to increased potato WP.

Table 5. Seasonal ANOVA summary table for assessed parameters over two production seasons.

Source of Variation	Duration of ¹ CCx	² ΔSWC	Rainfall	³ ETa	Yield	⁴ WP
Season (S)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.556	<0.001

Note: ¹ Maximum canopy cover, ² changes soil water content, ³ actual crop evapotranspiration, and ⁴ water productivity.

Table 6. Seasonal correlation of measured parameters across localities.

Source of Variation	Duration of ¹ CCx	² ETa	Yield	Rainfall	³ ΔSWC	⁴ WP
Duration of CCx	1	0.19 *	0.2178 *	0.23 *	0.009 ns	-0.01 ns
ETa		1	-0.01 ns	0.76 ***	0.32 ***	-0.64 ***

Table 6. Cont.

Source of Variation	Duration of ¹ CCx	² ETa	Yield	Rainfall	³ ΔSWC	⁴ WP
Yield			1	0.10 ns	−0.45 ***	0.74 ***
Rainfall				1	0.11 ***	−0.35 ***
SWC					1	−0.52 ***
WP						1

Note: ¹ Maximum canopy cover, ² actual crop evapotranspiration, ³ changes in soil water content, and ⁴ water productivity; ns, not significant; *, ($p < 0.05$) and ***, ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 3. Seasonal measured variables: water productivity (A), yield (B), crop actual evapotranspiration, ETa (C), rainfall (D), maximum canopy cover, CCx (E), and duration of maximum canopy cover (F). Error bars is the standard deviation, bars with the same letter differ non-significantly ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 4. Seasonal rainfall distribution according to growth stages for season 1 (2022/23) and season 2 (2023/24).

3.3. Soil Moisture Content and Drainage

The integration of cultivar \times mulch \times locality had an insignificant ($p > 0.05$) effect on rainfall and changes in soil water content (SWC); meanwhile, secondary integration cultivar \times locality significantly affected ($p < 0.05$) these two variables (Figure 5), and the results showed consistency over the growing seasons. All the treatments showed similar trends for SWC throughout the season, however, only treatments with the Panamera cultivar are shown in Figure 6. This cultivar was the last one to reach maturity and represent an entire season of SWC. Panamera with mulch (PM) was found to have higher changes in SWC across localities, with an average ranging from 44 to 126 mm, whereas Sababa (not mulched) (SNM) recorded the lowest changes in SWC, with a two-season average ranging from 31 to 97 mm. It was observed that mulch improved soil water storage, and, as a result, the mulched plots had higher SWC compared to the plots without a mulch treatment. Furthermore, high late-season rainfall resulted in higher water storage in the soil, causing high differences in SWC between planting and harvest. Drainage was minimal during the growing season for all localities; the uneven rain distribution and dry spells led to reduced drainage (Figure 5). For instance, when rain comes, it always finds the soil dry, except where there is mulch treatment. Therefore, rainwater must supply soil needs, then the surplus percolates downwards, which was mainly observed under mulch and towards the end of the season because soil moisture was near field capacity storage in these cases (Figure 6). In general, the late-maturing cultivar (Panamera) had higher drainage due to the high water available, and the crop was not using a lot of water at this stage (Figure 5). The other cultivars (Mondial, Electra, and Sababa) matured earlier than Panamera, as shown in Table 1; therefore, they experienced less drainage and the SWC was above field capacity storage once or twice in the season. In Mbalenhle, changes in SWC under mulch treatments were 7.9 to 21.6% higher compared to those without mulch treatments. Meanwhile, those in Mbhava and Stezi were higher by 15.7 to 20.0% and 5.8 to 24.7%, respectively. However, the positive effects of mulch, such as improved utilization and conservation of rainfall, were insignificant due to erratic rainfall and its distribution in soil water. Previous studies [10,11] also found higher soil water storage in treatments with mulch compared to those without mulch treatments. Therefore, it can be seen that mulch enhances soil moisture availability through the collection of ineffective rainfall, reducing soil evaporation and improving rainfall infiltration during heavy rains [10]. Soil water content differs across localities; this further shows that the localities had different soil properties (Table 3) and climates (Figure 2), leading to different SWCs. All localities received substantial rainfall for both seasons, and soil texture contributed to the observed differences. Mbhava and Stezi are in the same agroecological zone, however, where there were differences in SWC, this is attributed to non-climatic factors such as the high clay content in Mbhava (Table 3), which led to high water-holding capacity, whereas, in Stezi, the sandy soils resulted in higher drainage. Therefore, smallholder farmers can explore the practices of mulch application to improve soil moisture content in localities that have high drainage soils, considering rainfall variability under such settings. Hence, the practice will be valuable.

3.4. Actual Crop Evapotranspiration

The integration of cultivar \times mulch \times locality had an insignificant ($p > 0.05$) effect on crop evapotranspiration (ETa) (Figure 5), but secondary integration of cultivar \times locality significantly affected ($p < 0.05$) ETa. In Mbalenhle, the average ETa over the two seasons ranged from 343 to 449 mm; Mbhava, had a range of 451 to 543 mm; and, lastly, in Stezi it ranged from 390 to 453 mm. The mulch treatments had lower ETa than that for the no mulch treatments across the localities, however, the positive effect was insignificant, which might be attributed to the timing of the mulch applications. In the current study, mulch was applied before ridging in the establishment stage. However, mulch changed the water consumption patterns. Actual crop evapotranspiration is the sum of soil evaporation and crop transpiration, hence, treatments that do not have mulch have high ETa as a result

of high evaporation compared to treatments with mulch, where evaporation is minimal. Chen et al. [10] reported potato ETa of 216 to 278 mm under rainfed conditions, meanwhile, Karam et al. [35] reported 498 to 606 mm. The current study reported that ETa is in harmony with previously reported ETa. It was further observed that Mbhava had higher ETa than other localities, especially in the second season (Figure 5). In this locality, higher atmospheric water demand led to higher transpiration and soil evaporation, resulting in higher ETa. However, the plants were not able to use water efficiently, and a lot of it was lost to the atmosphere. In the current study, it was noted that the substantial rainfall received was not all used up by the crop, some of it drained away (Figure 5), especially under mulch treatments. The nature of the rainfall was erratic, with distribution being uneven, such that a large portion was received in one day or over three consecutive days; hence, plants were not able to use the rainfall efficiently due to the nature of it. High late-season rainfall contributed to high soil moisture storage, leading to high ETa for Panamera compared to Sababa, which is an early-maturing cultivar. Reducing ineffective water loss such as soil evaporation can improve potato ETa [36], however, this phenomenon can be appreciated under limited water availability. However, in the current study, little of it was witnessed. In general, the ETa effect of mulching cultivation practices will be much better in dry seasons than in wet seasons.

Figure 5. Localities’ seasonal rainfall, drainage, actual crop evapotranspiration (ETa), and changes in soil water content (SWC) for 2022/23 and 2023/2.

Figure 6. Soil water content (SWC) and rainfall for Mbalenhle, Mbhava, and Stezi for the 2022/23 and 2023/24 seasons. Field capacity (FC), permanent wilting point (PWP), and saturation (SAT).

3.5. Yield

The integration of locality \times cultivar had a significant ($p < 0.05$) effect on yield for both seasons and showed consistency (Table 7). Meanwhile, locality \times cultivar \times mulch had an insignificant ($p > 0.05$) effect on yield for both seasons, hence, the important integration for yield was cultivar \times locality. The results showed that localities with higher altitudes had a greater influence on yield. Mbalenhle (1003 m.a.s.l) had a higher yield for all treatments except Sababa with mulch, Mbalenhle had an yield average of 32.13 to 62.88 t ha⁻¹; followed by Stezi (874 m.a.s.l), where the average yield ranging from 31.33 to 55.07 t ha⁻¹; and, lastly, Mbhava (750 m.a.s.l) had low yields (24.85 to 41.18 t ha⁻¹) for the treatments (Table 7). Also, the results indicate that yields were more stable at higher altitudes compared to lower altitudes. Panamera yield was stable and performed very well at higher altitudes (Stezi and Mbalenhle) compared to lower altitudes (Mbhava). Electra kept overperforming over the two growing seasons across localities in high and low altitudes, having a yield range of 30.97 to 64.22 t ha⁻¹; the highest yield

(64.22 t ha⁻¹) was observed under mulch in Mbalenhle. Meanwhile, Panamera without a mulch treatment in Mbhava was the least performing, with a yield of 22.56 t ha⁻¹. Waqas et al. [37] reported potato yields of 29.44 to 49.65 t ha⁻¹, which is within the range of the current study. Furthermore, Das et al. [38] reported lower yields of different cultivars compared to the current study, ranging from 14.08 to 33.54 t ha⁻¹. The yield variation observed from these different studies is attributed to differences in climatic conditions across the agroecologies, the cultivars having different yield potentials and having different genetic modifications with different resistance levels to abiotic and biotic stresses, and, lastly, the management practices were different. In the current study, climatic conditions and soil texture contributed to the yield differences observed across localities. For instance, Mbhava's higher average daily vapor pressure deficit (VPD) (1.08–1.14 kPa) (Table 4) compared to that in Stezi (0.82 and 0.83) and Mbalenhle (0.78 and 0.74) led to a higher difference in atmospheric dryness, increasing water loss through higher transpiration (especially in C3 plants where stomatal control is not highly regulated) [14]. Also, higher altitude localities (Mbalenhle and Stezi) are on a sun-facing (north-facing) slope and are more exposed to direct sunlight, thereby improving plants' photosynthesis when compared to Mbhava, which is on a south-facing slope. Furthermore, rainfall received on consecutive days had a negative effect on the clay soils in Mbhava, compared to Stezi and Mbalenhle, which are dominated by sandy soils with higher drainage. The high water-holding capacity of clay contributed to tuber rotting in Mbhava, and, as a result, low yields were observed. Overall, Panamera and Electra were able to maintain the prolonged duration of CCx (Figure 7), resulting in a higher yield due to the long-maintained vegetative stage that allowed Panamera and Electra to accumulate more dry matter and increase tuber size.

Table 7. Yield, and water productivity (WP) for the 2022/23 and 2023/24 seasons for the three localities.

Locality	Cultivar	Mulching	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)			WP (kg m ⁻³)			
			2022/23	2023/24	Mean	2022/23	2023/24	Mean	
Mbalenhle	Electra	Mulch	61.53 g	64.22 f	62.88	18.38 j	17.84 e	18.11	
			Mondial	38.99 bcde	51.27 bcdef	45.13	13.34 hi	13.07 bcde	13.21
			Panamera	42.93 def	59.13 ef	51.03	12.94 hi	12.83 bcde	12.89
			Sababa	35.81 abcd	28.48 abc	32.15	10.25 defgh	8.50 abcd	9.38
	Electra	Not mulch	58.94 g	62.99 f	60.97	15.98 ij	16.06 cde	16.02	
			Mondial	37.05 abcde	53.66 cdef	45.36	11.68 fgh	12.76 bcde	12.22
			Panamera	40.32 cde	54.22 def	47.27	10.46 efgh	10.58 abcde	10.52
			Sababa	36.53 abcd	40.35 abcdef	38.44	10.52 efgh	10.82 abcde	10.67
Mbhava	Electra	Mulch	43.78 def	36.07 abcde	39.93	8.14 bcdef	8.97 abcd	8.56	
			Mondial	25.62 ab	27.66 ab	26.64	4.79 ab	7.52 ab	6.16
			Panamera	30.66 abc	27.32 ab	28.99	5.03 ab	5.18 ab	5.11
			Sababa	27.43 abc	30.69 abcd	29.06	5.01 ab	7.82 ab	6.42
	Electra	Not mulch	51.44 efg	30.97 abcd	41.21	9.29 cdefg	7.63 ab	8.46	
			Mondial	23.18 a	26.43 ab	24.81	4.20 a	6.59 ab	5.40
			Panamera	37.58 abcde	22.56 a	30.07	6.78 abcd	3.85 a	5.32
			Sababa	25.61 ab	32.45 abcd	29.03	4.66 ab	7.95 abc	6.31
Stezi	Electra	Mulch	59.99 g	50.17 bcdef	55.08	12.29 gh	16.21 de	14.25	
			Mondial	39.94 bcde	43.94 abcdef	41.94	7.90 bcde	16.28 de	12.09
			Panamera	33.71 abcd	37.17 abcde	35.44	5.01 ab	9.99 abcde	7.50
			Sababa	37.97 bcde	33.42 abcd	35.70	7.58 abcde	10.13 abcde	8.50
	Electra	Not mulch	56.69 fg	36.02 abcde	46.36	12.26 gh	10.80 abcde	11.53	
			Mondial	34.17 abcd	40.60 abcdef	37.39	6.22 abc	12.68 bcde	9.45
			Panamera	25.53 ab	40.66 abcdef	33.10	6.20 abc	11.20 abcde	8.70
			Sababa	44.35 def	32.56 abcd	38.45	8.790 cdefg	9.76 abcde	9.28

Note: Letters in columns that are not the same are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 7. Maximum canopy cover (CCx) of selected cultivars across localities [(A) 2022/23 and (B) 2023/24] and duration of CCx [(C) 2022/23 and (D) 2023/24]. Error bars is the standard deviation, bars with the same letter differ non-significantly ($p > 0.05$).

3.6. Water Productivity

The results showed that cultivar \times locality \times mulch interaction had an insignificant ($p > 0.05$) effect on water productivity (WP). Meanwhile, cultivar \times locality interaction had significant ($p < 0.001$) effects on WP (Table 7), therefore, WP was mainly influenced by cultivar and locality. Mbalenhle recorded a two-seasons' average WP of 8.50 to 18.38 kg m⁻³ across treatments, meanwhile, Mbhava and Stezi had a range of 4.20 to 7.95 kg m⁻³ and 5.01 to 16.28 kg m⁻³, respectively. The highest and statistically superior WP of potato (18.38 kg m⁻³) was achieved by Electra with mulch in Mbalenhle, and the lowest WP (3.85 kg m⁻³) was obtained by Panamera without mulch in Mbhava. In general, treatments that had Electra cultivar recorded a high two-season WP average compared to other cultivars across localities. Mthembu et al. [21] reported WP for the same cultivars as those used in the current study of 1.09 to 5.09 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mmol}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ as instantaneous water use efficiency at different growth stages. Meanwhile, Lindi et al. [2] and Ijaz-ul-Hassan et al. [3] reported potato WPs that were low and in line with the current study (3.56 to 8.70 kg m⁻³ and 14.60 to 17.28 kg m⁻³, respectively). Kassaye et al. [39] reported potato WP of 8.73 to 28.06 kg m⁻³. The current study's WP values are in harmony with previously reported values. The variation between these WPs is attributed to the different ETa of cultivars and the yield, which was influenced by soil type, management practices, and climatic conditions because these studies were conducted in different environments. In the current study, WP was found to be directly proportional to yield and it decreased with increased ETa. As mentioned above, rainfall was more erratic, such that the early-maturing cultivar's (Sababa) WP was more influenced by ETa than yield, and this was due to the low rainfall received from planting to harvest for this cultivar compared to that received

for the other cultivars. Panamera resulted in lower WP, indicating that the consumption of huge amounts of rainfall water did not translate into higher yield, hence, this cultivar did not use water efficiently. Moreover, the increase in WP with Electra is ascribed to the reduced amount used without a significant reduction in potato tuber yield. Furthermore, climatic conditions such as low VPD, high drainage, and high relative humidity in Stezi and Mbalenhle affected ETa positively by lowering atmospheric water demand, and, in the presence of high rainfall, sandy soils allowed drainage, consequently resulting in a higher yield, which translated to higher WP. It was the opposite in Mbhava; higher VPD led to reduced crop transpiration. It is worth noting that localities that are at high elevations with sandy soil texture (Mbalenhle and Stezi) showed a more stable response between years for WP. The only source of water in these agroecologies is rainfall, which shows uneven distribution and puts resource-constrained potato farming at risk. Therefore, to be resilience and improve WP under these conditions, the selection of cultivars that use less water and produce a high yield are “low-hanging fruits” for improving potato WP and choosing climatic conditions that have proportionality of rainfall and crop coefficient, with less atmospheric dryness, are very important. Cultivars such as Sababa have low ETa but produce low yields, resulting in low WP. Electra was consistent over the two growing seasons and across localities, indicating that this cultivar has a wide range of environmental adaptations that can withstand frequent dry spells and be able to produce high yields. Farmers in such settings can adopt the practices of using Electra with mulch under sandy soils and Electra without mulch under soils with a high percentage of clay to improve potato WP.

4. Conclusions

The influence of rainfall, soil water content, canopy development, and water used, suggest that potato WP can be increased by applying practices that conserve soil moisture, considering the risks of climatic variability. The three-way integration of cultivar selection, locality, and mulch application did not statistically alter rainfed potato water productivity since mulch inclusion did not yield an advantage. We postulate that the three-way interaction may significantly alter rainfed potato water productivity given low-rainfall seasons where potatoes may be subjected to water scarcity; also, mulch should be applied immediately after planting. However, the secondary integration of cultivar selection and locality significantly altered potato water productivity in both seasons. Electra cultivar consistently produced higher yield resulting higher water productivity across both planting seasons. Out of the three drought-tolerant cultivars (Electra, Mondial, and Sababa), Electra showed stability and good yield performance even under the dry spells that were experienced, and WP stability across agroecologies. Mbalenhle’s high humidity reduced atmospheric dryness, and high drainage of this locality soil, contributed to, produce high yield returns per water used. Micro-climatic conditions (Stezi and Mbhava) produced the unexpected results of statistically superior WP in Stezi compared to Mbhava; also, higher VPD and low drainage in Mbhava lowered WP through restricted crop transpiration and high soil water storage. Electra is recommended for production in these zones due to water productivity stability in various agroecologies, and the WP was mainly caused by higher yield. Considering the uneven distribution of rainfall, shifting planting dates can be an option to make use of late-season rainfall.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, N.P.M.P. and S.T.H.; methodology, N.P.M.P., S.T.H., and L.S.; validation and formal analysis, N.P.M.P., S.T.H., and L.S.; resources and software, N.Z.N.; writing—original draft preparation, N.P.M.P. and S.T.H.; writing—review and editing N.P.M.P., S.T.H., E.S.-G., L.S., and N.Z.N.; supervision, S.T.H., E.S.-G., and N.Z.N.; project administration and funding acquisition N.Z.N. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This project was funded by the National Research Foundation (NRF) grant No. 134115 and European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme to cover running costs, under grant agreement No. 862555. Potatoes South Africa to provide a scholarship for N.P.M.

Data Availability Statement: Available upon request.

Acknowledgments: Wesgrow (Pty) Ltd. for assisting with potato seeds. Department of Agriculture and Rural Development and extension officers from Allerton office, Pietermaritzburg. Farmers from Swayimane and Appelsbosch. Mthokozisi “Shenge” Buthelezi for assisting with maps. Lastly, Morgan Nadioo, the assistant project manager, for project implementation and guidance in data collecting.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Mabhaudhi, T.; Mpandeli, S.; Luxon, N.; Chimonyo, V.G.P.; Senzanje, A.; Modi, A.T. Options for Improving Agricultural Water Productivity Under Increasing Water Scarcity in South Africa. In Proceedings of the 3rd World Irrigation Forum (WIF3) on Development for Water, Food and Nutrition Security in a Competitive Environment, Bali, Indonesia, 1–7 September 2019.
- Lindi, S.; Iticha, B.; Hone, M. Effect of Moisture Stress at Different Growth Stage on Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Yield and Water Productivity at Kulumsa, Ethiopia. *Irrig. Drain. Syst. Eng.* **2021**, *10*, 3–6.
- Ijaz-Ul-hassan, S.; Khan, A.; Erum, S. Effect of deficit drip irrigation on yield and water productivity of potato crop. *Int. J. Agric. Ext.* **2021**, *9*, 239–244. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Muthoni, J.; Shimelis, H. Chapter 24—An Overview of Potato Production in Africa. In *Potato production worldwide*; Caliskan, M.E., Bakhsh, A., Jabran, K., Eds.; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2023; pp. 435–456. [[CrossRef](#)]
- van Steenberg, F.; Mulder, E.; Bremer, K.; Mul, M.; Chukalla, A.; Chevalking, S.; Deligianni, A.; van der Plujim, L.; Deribe, M. *Compendium of Approaches to Improve Water Productivity*; Water-PIP Technical Report Series; IHE Delft Institute for Water Education: Delft, The Netherlands, 2022.
- Allen, R.G.; Pereira, L.S. *Crop Evapotranspiration Guidelines for Computing Crop Water Requirements*; FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No.56; FAO: Rome, Italy, 1998; ISBN 9251042195.
- Ndayakunze, A. *Optimising Rainfall Utilisation in Dryland Crop Production: A Case of Shallow-Rooted Crop*; University of Pretoria: Pretoria, South Africa, 2014.
- Kader, M.A.; Singha, A.; Begum, M.A.; Jewel, A.; Khan, F.H.; Khan, N.I. Mulching as water-saving technique in dryland agriculture: Review article. *Bull. Natl. Res. Cent.* **2019**, *43*, 147. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Zayton, A.; Guirguis, A.; Allam, K. Effect of Mulching Type and Duration on the Productivity and Water Use Efficiency of Potato. *J. Soil Sci. Agric. Eng.* **2015**, *6*, 719–733. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Chen, Y.; Chai, S.; Tian, H.; Chai, Y.; Li, Y.; Chang, L. Straw strips mulch on furrows improves water use efficiency and yield of potato in a rainfed semiarid area. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2019**, *211*, 142–151. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Brar, A.S.; Buttar, G.S.; Thind, H.S.; Singh, K.B. Improvement of Water Productivity, Economics and Energetics of Potato through Straw Mulching and Irrigation Scheduling in Indian Punjab. *Potato Res.* **2019**, *62*, 465–484. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Zhang, S.; Wang, H.; Sun, X.; Fan, J.; Zhang, F.; Zheng, J.; Li, Y. Effects of farming practices on yield and crop water productivity of wheat, maize and potato in China: A meta-analysis. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2021**, *243*, 106444. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Biswal, P.; Swain, D.K.; Jha, M.K. Straw mulch with limited drip irrigation influenced soil microclimate in improving tuber yield and water productivity of potato in subtropical India. *Soil Tillage Res.* **2022**, *223*, 105484. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Trapero-mozos, A.; Morris, W.L.; Ducreux, L.J.M.; Mclean, K.; Stephens, J.; Torrance, L.; Bryan, G.J.; Hancock, R.D.; Taylor, M.A. Engineering heat tolerance in potato by temperature-dependent expression of a specific allele of heat-shock cognate. *Plant Biotechnol. J.* **2018**, *70*, 197–207. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
- Thuo, C.M.; Maina, S.W. Strengthening smallholder farmers resiliency for improved sustainable productivity of Irish Potatoes in Kenya. *World J. Adv. Res. Rev.* **2024**, *22*, 512–520. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Thomas-sharma, S.; Abdurahman, A.; Ali, S.; Andrade-piedra, J.L.; Bao, S. Seed degeneration in potato: The need for an integrated seed health strategy to mitigate the problem in developing countries. *Plant Pathol.* **2016**, *65*, 3–16. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Mabhaudhi, T.; Nhamo, L.; Mpandeli, S. *Enhancing Crop Water Productivity Under Increasing Water Scarcity in South Africa*; Elsevier Inc.: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2021. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Wolfe, D.W.; Fereres, E.; Voss, R.E. Growth and yield response of two potato cultivars to various levels of applied water. *Irrig. Sci.* **1983**, *3*, 211–222. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Fandika, I.R.; Kemp, P.D.; Millner, J.P.; Horne, D.; Roskrige, N. Irrigation and nitrogen effects on tuber yield and water use efficiency of heritage and modern potato cultivars. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2016**, *170*, 148–157. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Ngobese, N.Z.; Naidoo, M.; Workneh, T.S. Yield and tuber quality performance of eight European potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) cultivars in a short-day temperate climate. *J. Cent. Eur. Agric.* **2022**, *23*, 807–816. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Mthembu, S.G.; Magwaza, L.S.; Mashilo, J.; Mditshwa, A.; Odindo, A. Drought tolerance assessment of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) genotypes at different growth stages, based on morphological and physiological traits. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2022**, *261*, 107361. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Soil Classification Working Group Soil Classification: A National and Anthropogenic System for South Africa, 3rd ed. Agricultural Research Council Institute for Soil, Climate and Water: Pretoria, South Africa, 2018; pp. 77–81.
- Saxton, K.E.; Willey, P.H. The SPAW model for agricultural field and pond hydrologic simulation. In *Watershed Model*; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2005; pp. 401–435. [[CrossRef](#)]

24. Ndlovu, H.S.; Odindi, J.; Sibanda, M.; Mutanga, O.; Clulow, A.; Chimonyo, V.G.P.; Mabhaudhi, T. A Comparative Estimation of Maize Leaf Water Content Using Machine Learning Techniques and Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)—Based Proximal and Remotely Sensed Data. *Remote Sens.* **2021**, *13*, 4091. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Tamako, N.; Thamaga-Chitja, J.M. Does social capital play a role in climate change adaptation among smallholder farmers for improving food security and livelihoods? *J. Consum. Sci.* **2017**, *2*, 16–26.
26. Popoola, A.Q. Using Agrometeorological Data to Equip Local Farmers for Sustainable Food Production in Swayimane, KwaZulu-Natal. Doctoral Dissertation, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa, 2019.
27. Mthembu, S.G. Response of Potato Genotypes to Production Sites and Water Deficit Imposed at Different Growth Stages, University of KwaZulu-Natal. Master's Dissertation, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa, 2020.
28. Manson, A.D.; Bainbridge, S.H.; Thibaud, G.R. *Methods Used for Analysis of Soils and Plant Material by Analytical Services at Cedara*; KZN Agri-Report No. N/A2020/07; KZN Department of Agriculture & Rural Development: Pietermaritzburg, South Africa, 2020.
29. Phungula, N.P.M.; Hadebe, S.; Schulte-Geldermann, E.; Ngobese, N.Z. *Morphological Response of Four Potato Cultivars (Solanum tuberosum L.) Cultivars to Different Agriculture Practices Under Rainfed Production, Proceeding of the Acta Hort.1391. ISHS 2024: Proc. IX South-Eastern Europe Symposium on Vegetables and Potatoes; ISHS Acta Horticulturae: Leuven, Belgium, 2024; pp. 131–138.* [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Mukiibi, A.; Franke, A.C.; Steyn, J.M. Determination of Crop Coefficients and Evapotranspiration of Potato in a Semi-Arid Climate Using Canopy State Variables and Satellite-Based NDVI. *Remote Sens.* **2023**, *15*, 4579. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. Sahoo, P.; Brar, A.S.; Sharma, S. Effect of methods of irrigation and sulphur nutrition on seed yield, economic and bio-physical water productivity of two sun fl ower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) hybrids. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2018**, *206*, 158–164. [[CrossRef](#)]
32. Machakaire, A.T.B.; Steyn, J.M.; Franke, A.C. Photosynthesis rate, radiation and water use efficiencies of irrigated potato in a semi-arid climate using Eddy Covariance techniques. *J. Agric. Sci.* **2023**, *161*, 217–229. [[CrossRef](#)]
33. Naidoo, M.; van Rij, N.; Arathoon, J. *Potato Production for KwazZulu-Natal*; Agriculture Update; KZN Department of Agriculture, Environmental Affairs and Rural Development: Pietermaritzburg, South Africa, 2010.
34. Sarker, K.K.; Hossain, A.; Timsina, J.; Biswas, S.K.; Kundu, B.C.; Barman, A.; Murad, K.F.I.; Akter, F. Yield and quality of potato tuber and its water productivity are influenced by alternate furrow irrigation in a raised bed system. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2019**, *224*, 105750. [[CrossRef](#)]
35. Karam, F.; Amacha, N.; Fahed, S.; Asmar, T.E.L.; Domínguez, A. Response of potato to full and deficit irrigation under semiarid climate: Agronomic and economic implications. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2014**, *142*, 144–151. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Li, R.; Chai, S.; Chai, Y.; Li, Y.; Lan, X.; Ma, J. Mulching optimizes water consumption characteristics and improves crop water productivity on the semi-arid Loess Plateau of China. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2021**, *254*, 106965. [[CrossRef](#)]
37. Waqas, M.S.; Cheema, M.J.M.; Hussain, S.; Ullah, M.K.; Iqbal, M.M. Delayed irrigation: An approach to enhance crop water productivity and to investigate its effects on potato yield and growth parameters. *Agric. Water Manag.* **2021**, *245*, 106576. [[CrossRef](#)]
38. Das, S.; Mitra, B.; Luthra, S.K.; Saha, A.; Hassan, M.M. Study on Morphological, Physiological Characteristics and Yields of Twenty-One Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) Cultivars Grown in Eastern Sub-Himalayan Plains of India. *Agronomy* **2021**, *11*, 335. [[CrossRef](#)]
39. Kassaye, K.T.; Yilma, W.A.; Fisha, M.H.; Haile, D.H. Yield and Water Use Efficiency of Potato under Alternate Furrows and Deficit Irrigation. *Int. J. Agron.* **2020**, *2020*, 8869098. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.